

Comparing Think-aloud to a Decision-making Characteristic Questionnaire in Clinical Judgments

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Item Development Process

Clinical Judgment

Clinical judgment is an opinion formed through a decision-making process that relies on healthcare knowledge and skills. Using clinical judgment to select the best possible evidence-based solution after identifying and evaluating alternative care options leads to controlling risks and delivering high-quality care.

Results

Pilot Item

Current Research

- Compare and contrast two protocols for evaluating clinical judgment pilot items
 - Think aloud paradigm
 - Decision-making Characteristic Questionnaire (DMCQ)

Think aloud

- Semi-structured interview
- Participants engages with pilot items
 - Verbally describe where their attention is drawn
- Experimenter observe participants
 - Clarify participant descriptions in terms of measured construct

DMCQ

- Explicitly probes decision-making process
- Subjective 3-pt Likert scale
- Answering this item requires me to:
 - Filter irrelevant information
 - Draw inferences
 - Compare and contrast content
 - Prioritize information

Results

- Think aloud provided qualitatively rich descriptions
 - Required observer interaction for clarification
 - 15 min per item
- DMCQ provided similar patterns across the clinical judgment components
 - 4 min per item

Implications

- Think aloud:
 - More complex data; participants have an opportunity to express their entire thought process
 - Resource intense; requires observer and independent coders
- DMCQ:
 - Efficient method of collecting specified information
 - Requires validation